

First Marker Feedback	
(C1) General structure, formatting, and Layout.Grammar and Spelling, Writing Style (5%)	The thesis was well written with a few mistakes identified. The Scope of the Study should lead to the boundaries and limitations of the proposed implementation and not the structure of writing the organizational structure of the work.
(C2) Introduction (10%)	The thesis should highlight the core objective of how Digital Footprinting was implemented, along with its benefits.
(C3) Literature Review (15%)	The limitations and the research gaps in the existing works corresponding to the Literature Review were adequately explained.
(C4) Research Methods (20%)	The methodology is explained with proper justifications. However, it can be improved with quality and performance measures to be used in the proposed work.
(C5) Experiments, Implementation, Tools, Development, Simulation etc (20%)	The implementation was done effectively done on Tokenizer, Data Transformer, Formal Language Specification, and simulated with Demo URL
(C6) Results, Analysis, Findings, & Discussion (15%)	The learner effectively communicated the problem statement, results and findings of the proposed work, ensuring the viewer understood the objectives clearly.
(C7) Conclusion, Implication, & Recommendations (10%)	The conclusion was defined appropriately based on the discussions on the proposed work. Some specific outcomes concerning the scalability and performance metrics could improve the credibility of the thesis in a better way.
(C8) Citation & references (5%)	The learner could have highlighted the core paper that is taken for the proposed work.

Second Marker Feedback	
(C1) General structure, formatting, and Layout.Grammar and Spelling, Writing Style (5%)	A report have been produced of a good structure containing with all required sections and pleasing referencing. Generally good, clear and consistent professional writing supported by plots, figures and tables wherever necessary.
(C2) Introduction (10%)	The introduction of the problem is not clearly outlining the purpose of the study. Please revisit this and provide a clear objective behind the problem.
(C3) Literature Review (15%)	The literature review citation are not cited correctly, Some Provided References are outdated. Recent techniques or methods needs to be discussed here rather than focusing on well known facts and formulae
(C4) Research Methods (20%)	Very good experiment and evidence of appropriate implementation or development, use of appropriate and relevant tools and resources professionally, with a complete report of experiments
(C5) Experiments, Implementation, Tools, Development, Simulation etc (20%)	Very good experiment and evidence of appropriate implementation or development, use of appropriate and relevant tools and resources professionally, with a complete report of experiments.
(C6) Results, Analysis, Findings, & Discussion (15%)	Satisfactory results with discussion but no critical analyses are provided, still need improvement.
(C7) Conclusion, Implication, & Recommendations (10%)	The conclusions and future directions need to be written precisely. The novelty of the research should be highlighted
(C8) Citation & references (5%)	Citations are cited correctly, and references are recent, up to date and reliable sources with correct format.